

Insect Indicators of Soil Quality: Unveiling the Underground Tapestry

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Introduction

Living things alone have “health” so before discussing about “soil health”, we need to acknowledge that the soil is alive! As per the USDA-NRCS definition, “Soil health is the continued capacity of a soil to function as a vital living ecosystem that sustains plants, animals, and humans.” The precise biological life in the Soil is the key indicator of good soil health. A healthy soil should be full of earthworms, varied soil arthropods include beetles, spiders, ants, and other soil life confining to the top six inches. Healthy soils largely have live plants thriving continuous to feed soil microbes and other soil as well as terrestrial arthropods. Soil arthropods constitute a varied and rich community in the soil, playing their significant key roles in various ecological processes. Their response to fluctuations in the varied soil conditions makes them valued bio-indicators, reflecting alterations in the environment that may not be immediately apparent through conventional assessments. This article combines current research on soil-dwelling insects, emphasizing their potential as sensitive indicators of soil quality.

Various insect taxa, such as ground beetles, ants, termites, and springtails, exhibit distinct responses to shifts in soil properties, including organic matter content, moisture levels, and nutrient availability. By monitoring changes in insect community composition and behavior, researchers gain insights into the intricate relationships between soil health and biodiversity.

Practical applications of insect indicators in soil quality assessments are discussed, highlighting their relevance in agriculture, ecosystem restoration, and urban planning. Leveraging the ecological services provided by these insects can enhance our ability to evaluate

soil health and implement targeted interventions. For instance, certain beetle species may indicate soil compaction, while ant diversity could signal changes in soil moisture levels.

Despite their potential, challenges in utilizing insect indicators are acknowledged. Mobility, species-specific responses, and potential confounding factors are considered, emphasizing the need for standardized protocols. The article also explores emerging technologies, such as DNA metabarcoding, to refine and streamline insect-based soil assessments.

Types of measures of soil and litter arthropods indicating soil quality and health with their challenges

Several soil and litter arthropods counting collembolan, Oribatida, Isopoda and Diplopoda living a rather sedentary life and hence reflect local conditions of a habitat (Van Straalen, 1998). These facts have been documented since long time, and associations between soil types and soil with litter arthropods have been established in various studies (Rusek, 1989). Usage of soil and litter arthropods as indicators of soil quality and health has commonly been done by gaging different properties and state in soil like litter arthropod biomass, density, abundance, species richness, and biological indices (Yeates & Bongers, 1997; Foissner, 1994) of either single taxon groups or of the total community (Aspetti et al., 2010).

In recent time, a simplified ecomorphological index (EMI) built on the morphology of micro-arthropods has been introduced (Parisi & Menta, 2008). Which can be used to assess soil quality and health based on the groups that are residing in the very soil samples, each taxonomic groups receive an EMI score from 1 to 20 (Table 1), conferring to its adaptability to the soil environment. Soil living forms residing deep are given an EMI score of 20 and intermediate forms are provided with a score proportional to their degree of concentration, whereas surface-roving forms are counted with an EMI equal to 1 (Parisi et al., 2005). The Biological Quality of Soil Index (BQS) is considered as the sum of EMI scores and soil quality correlates with the number of sets of arthropods having high EMI scores.

Table 1: Ecomorphological indices (EMIs) of the edaphic micro-arthropod groups (Parisi *et al.*, 2005).

Group	EMI Score	Group	EMI Score
Blattaria	5	Acari	20
Coleoptera	1-20	Araneae	1-5
Collembola	1-20	Opiliones	10
Diplura	20	Isopoda	10
Diptera (larvae)	10	Chilopoda	10-20
Embioptera	10	Palpigradi	20

Hemiptera	1-10	Diplopoda	10-20
Hymenoptera	1-5	Pauropoda	20
Orthoptera	1-20	Symphyla	20
Other holometabolous insects (adults)	1	Dermaptera	1
Other holometabolous insects (larvae)	10	Psocoptera	1
Protura	20	Microcoryphia	10
Thysanoptera	1	Zygentomata	10

Conclusion

Recognizing insects as indicators of soil quality adds a nuanced dimension to our understanding of ecosystem dynamics. Their role in reflecting the health of soils, often referred to as the 'underground tapestry,' underscores the importance of holistic approaches to soil management. Incorporating insect indicators into soil quality assessments not only enriches our comprehension of soil health but also offers sustainable solutions for preserving this vital resource for future generations.

The diversity of Soil arthropod, distribution and their abundance are determined by several factors that includes organic matter content, soil features, cover vegetation, soil disturbance (mechanical soil tillage), fire, and the pollution. Additionally, the diverse taxa respond differently to a variety of environmental factors. Some groups are more delicate, whereas others are abundant and more able to react to soil degradation. In addition, different species belonging to the same taxonomic group can respond differently.

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